

PLANT SPECIMENS PACKAGING PROCEDURE

I: Herbarium Specimens

Aim

To have strong and protective prepared parcel as to avoid damage of plant specimens during transit processes.

Materials:

Cut board; Plastic sheets; Bubble wrap; Brown gummed paper; Boxes: 2, 3,4, 6, & 7. Size 8 upwards for herbarium supplies.

Masking tape; 12 mm parcel tape or string; Tracking stickers

Packaging:

- Select suitable box size.
- Not more than 100 specimens per box.
- Wrap the bundle with bubble plastic wrapper
- Select suitable box size.
- All empty spaces filled with packaging material (e.g. shredded paper).
- Place the sample collection datasheet and other lists or forms on top.
- Seal the box with brown gum paper or brown masking tape.
- Wrapped in tar (waterproof paper)
- Box tied with plastic packaging straps
- Stick necessary documents on the parcels (tracking sticker, customs form, address and addressee and fragile stickers.)
- Weigh the parcel and fill the mass in where required

II: SHIPPING GUIDELINES FOR SILICA DRIED TISSUE FOR DNA BIOBANK

Step 1: Prepare tissue for DNA extraction:

- Place 3-5 leaf pieces of about 3x5 cm in an archival quality coin envelope labeled with sample information per individual sample. For plants with smaller leaves, i.e. ericoids, provide enough material to equate a leaf area of 5 – 10cm².
- Submit at least three replicates/sample (where available)
- Each sample should be labelled with:
 - Collector number
 - Taxonomic name
 - Sample number (if there are duplicates of each, write numbers on each bag accordingly, i.e. 1 of 4, 2 of 4, 3 of 4, 4 of 4)
 - Collector's name
- Tissue from each individual should be placed in archival grade coin envelopes and stored in sealed containers/Ziploc bags with silica gel (self-indicating beads are recommended) for long-term archival storage
- Store samples in the dark.

Step 2: Labelling

- Properly label samples and carefully print the address of the sender and recipient along with the contact information on the shipping box.
- Include all the special handling instructions, tracking number, plant species, and quantity of samples.

Step 3: Packaging

- Choose the most appropriate containers suitable for the type of samples being shipped, such as vials, tubes, bags, or boxes.
- Samples must be dried prior to shipping. Undried samples must be free from mold/contaminants and shipped in silica gel desiccant.
- (Silica) dried tissue samples from each individual should be placed in a plastic Ziploc bag with sufficient silica gel to keep the tissue dry. Using indicating silica gel will help determine if silica gel needs to be replaced or reactivated.
- Use bubble wrap (or other cushioning material) when sending samples, to prevent shifting of the samples and minimize the risk of sample damage during transit.

Step 4: Documentation

The documents you need depend on your sample organism and where you are sending your samples from. You may need to provide:

- Include a detailed packaging list with a description of each sample.
- Clarify the quantity of the samples and provide all the permits.
- Metadata: for each individual sample, copies of field collection sheets and relevant collector notes can be included in the shipping box or submitted electronically (via email); photos (when available) can be submitted in a Zipped folder via email or via WeTransfer.

Step 5: Shipping method

- Choose a suitable shipping method that aligns with the urgency of the shipment and any special requirements.
- Keep a record of the tracking number provided by the shipping service to monitor the progress of the shipment.
- Track the status of the shipment online and address any issues promptly.
- Inform the Biobank Curator about the tracking number and the expected delivery date of shipment.
- Shipments should only be delivered from Monday to Friday; avoid shipments arriving on Saturdays, Sundays, or national holidays.

Ship the samples to:

SANBI: Plant Tissue and DNA Biobank
Pretoria National Botanical Gardens: Herbarium Building
2 Cussonia Avenue
Brummeria
Pretoria
0184
+27734600942

Attention: Dr M. Mavhunga